

STUDIES ON HYDROFLUORENE DERIVATIVES. PART I. SYNTHESIS
OF 1:2:3:4:10:11-HEXAHYDROFLUORENE-2-ONE

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2-Indanone has been prepared by the Curtius degradation of indene-2-carboxylic acid. The Mannich-Robinson reaction with ethyl hydrind-2-one-1-carboxylate furnishes the desired product (III) in low yield; (III), after cyclisation and decarboxylation, yields 1:2:3:4-tetrahydrofluorene-2-one (IV). (IV) on catalytic reduction affords 1:2:3:4:10:11-hexahydrofluorene-2-one (II). The condensation of methyl 1-keto-2-indanylacetate with methyl succinate yields an acidic material which after esterification furnishes the desired product (V). This, on decarboxylation, followed by esterification and catalytic hydrogenation, furnishes the saturated di-ester (VII) which, on the Dieckmann cyclisation, followed by acid treatment, affords the same hexahydrofluorene-2-one (II).

With a view to synthesising the phenol (I), obtained as a degradation product of jervine (Fried *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 2970; cf. Fried and Klingsberg, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 4929), some pilot experiments are described below.

In our previous paper (Chatterjee, Chatterjee and Bhattacharyya, this *Journal*, 1958, 38, 391) it was noted that the Mannich-Robinson reaction of a mixture of methyl-5-methoxyhydrind-2-one-1- and -5-carboxylates with 1-diethylaminobutane-3 did not furnish any promising result. But the same reaction with ethyl hydrind-2-one-1-carboxylate afforded the desired product (III) in low yield even when two moles of the β -keto ester were used for one mole of the methiodide. Cyclisation and decarboxylation of the compound (III) with aqueous alkali resulted in a polymerised product. However, when treated with a mixture of acetic and hydrochloric acids (cf. Wilds and Shunk, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 469; Chatterjee and Bhattacharyya, this *Journal*, 1958, 38, 19), it afforded 1:2:3:4-tetrahydrofluorene-2-one (IV) in poor yield. The ultraviolet absorption spectrum, λ_{max} 257 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.07), establishes the location of the double bond at 10:11 positions. The unsaturated compound (IV), which was rather unstable, on hydrogenation over palladium catalyst, furnished the saturated compound (II). The latter compound, on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride, followed by dehydrogenation with selenium, afforded fluorene.

Because of the low yield of this step and our previous experience (Chatterjee, Chatterjee and Bhattacharyya, *loc. cit.*), the Mannich-Robinson reaction with indan-2-one, prepared by the Curtius degradation of indene-2-carboxylic acid, was not attempted.

Since the overall yield in the aforementioned preparation of 1:2:3:4:10:11-hexahydrofluorene-2-one is extremely low, another successful synthesis of the compound (II) is reported below.

Although the Stobbe condensations of indan-1-one (Clemo *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 863) and 4-methylindan-1-one (Howell and Taylor, *ibid.*, 1957, 3011) had always yielded the desired products in low yield, the condensation of methyl succinate with methyl 1-keto-2-indanylacetate according to the procedure of Johnson *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2395) afforded an acidic product, which after esterification with diazomethane furnished the desired condensation product (V) in about 40% yield. The ultraviolet absorption spectrum, $\lambda_{\max}$ 272 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.1), is indicative of the presence of cinnamic ester system in the compound (V). Treatment of the compound (V) with a mixture of acetic acid, hydrobromic acid and water, following the procedure of Johnson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), furnished a crystalline acid (VI: R = H). The ultraviolet spectra of this acid, $\lambda_{\max}$ 259 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.00), and of its dimethyl ester, $\lambda_{\max}$ 257 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.06), indicate that the double bond has shifted from its exocyclic position into the cyclopentane ring. The compound (VI: R = Me) was hydrogenated over palladium charcoal catalyst and the saturated ester (VII), thus obtained, was cyclised with sodium methoxide or by sodium hydride to furnish a β -keto ester, which on hydrolysis and decarboxylation afforded the ketone (II).

Further work along this line is in progress.

* EXPERIMENTAL

2-Indanone

For the preparation of indene-2-carboxylic acid, we essentially followed the method of Auwers (*Annalen*, 1918, 418, 167). But as the yields of the formyl

* All m.p. s are uncorrected. The ultraviolet absorption spectrum was examined in 95% ethanol by the Unicam spectrophotometer SP 500.

compound and indene-2-carboxylic acid have not been reported, the preparation of the formyl compound and the cyclisation of the latter by a modification of the original method are described below.

To sodium dust (2.3 g.) and a drop of methanol in benzene (45 c.c.), cooled to -10° , was added a mixture of ethyl β -phenylpropionate (8.9 g.) and ethyl formate (8 c.c.) in ether (30 c.c.) with shaking under nitrogen atmosphere, and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 48 hours. It was worked up and distilled, b.p. $105-10^{\circ}/2$ mm, yield 5.2 g. (reported b.p. $142^{\circ}/14$ mm; V. Auwers, *loc. cit.*).

To a stirred mixture of H_2SO_4 (conc., 200 c.c.) and phosphoric acid (85%, 60 c.c.), cooled to -10° , was added dropwise the above formyl compound (20 g.). After the completion of the addition, the stirring was continued for 2 hours. The dark red reaction product was poured into crushed ice and the product was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with sodium bicarbonate, dried and distilled to furnish ethyl indene-2-carboxylate (8 g.), b.p. $118^{\circ}/2$ mm; m.p. 50° (reported m.p. 57°). The alkaline aqueous layer was acidified to furnish indene-2-carboxylic acid (3 g.), m.p. $230-34^{\circ}$ (reported m.p. 234°). The ester was hydrolysed with 1:1 sulphuric acid by refluxing under nitrogen for 2 hours.

The acid (0.5 g.) was treated with thionyl chloride (0.5 c.c.) and a drop of pyridine in ether (15 c.c.). After removal of the ether, the residue (0.5 g.) was dissolved in dry acetone (6 c.c.) and cooled in an ice-bath. To the solution of the acid chloride was added a solution of potassium azide (0.3 g.) in water (0.8 c.c.) with shaking, when a white pasty material separated out. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 15 minutes in the cold and then diluted with water (14 c.c.). The precipitated solid was filtered and washed once with water and dried, m.p. $97-100^{\circ}$ (decomp.), yield 0.5 g. A mixture of the crude azide (0.5 g.) and ethanol (7 c.c.) was refluxed for 2 hours. After removal of the ethanol, the residue was evaporatively distilled at $150^{\circ}/4$ mm to furnish a crystalline material which on crystallisation from a mixture of acetone and petroleum ether yielded the pure material (0.25 g.), m.p. 155° . (Found: N, 6.9. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 6.89%).

A mixture of the above urethane (0.2 g.) and 2-N-HCl (140 c.c.) was distilled when the solid ketone came out with steam. The ketone was extracted with ether and after evaporation of the ether, the residue was converted into the semicarbazone. The crude semicarbazone (0.14 g.) was crystallised from alcohol to furnish the pure material, m.p. 218° (reported m.p. 218° ; Thorpe, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 128). (Found: N, 22.23. (Calc. for $C_{10}H_{11}ON_3$: N, 22.22%).

3-Carboethoxy-3-butan-3'-onyl indan-2-one (III).—Xylene bromide, prepared by the method of Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1888, 83, 5) was converted into phenylene-diacetonitrile according to the method of Moore and Thorpe (*ibid.*, 1908, 98, 175). Phenylenediacetic acid was prepared from the above dinitrile, following the procedure of Perkin and Titley (*ibid.*, 1922, 121, 1562). Ethyl 2-hydrindone-1-carboxylate was obtained by the Dieckmann cyclisation of diethylphenylene diacetate according to the method of Carrick and Fry (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 4386).

To the sodio enolate, prepared from the above β -keto ester (10 g.) and sodium dust (0.79 g.) in dry benzene (150 c.c.), was added, under nitrogen atmosphere, the methiodide of 1-diethylamino-3-butanone (4.3 g. of base), dissolved in absolute alcohol (10 c.c.). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 16 hours at room temperature and refluxed for 1 hour. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into ice-water. The benzene layer was washed successively with water, NaOH solution (5 %) and finally with water. The combined aqueous layer and the above washings on acidification with iced HCl furnished the unchanged β -keto ester (3.4 g.). The benzene solution was dried and evaporated. The residue, thus obtained, was evaporatively distilled at $130^{\circ}/0.1$ mm to yield a white crystalline solid (2.8 g.) containing some oily material which was further purified by crystallisation from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether ($40-60^{\circ}$) to afford a crystalline material (2.3 g.), m.p. $78-79^{\circ}$. This material even on repeated crystallisation always gave a lower analytical value for carbon and hydrogen. A portion of the above material (750 mg.) was chromatographed on alumina (30 g.) using petroleum ether ($60-80^{\circ}$) as the eluting solvent. The liquid fraction (350 mg.), thus obtained, soon solidified. A portion of this solid (200 mg.) was crystallised three times from petroleum ether ($40-60^{\circ}$) to furnish a material, m.p. $79-79.5^{\circ}$, which was evaporatively distilled at $125^{\circ}/0.2$ mm for analysis. (Found: C, 70.31; H, 6.30. $C_{16}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 70.07; H, 6.56%).

1 : 2 : 3 : 4-Tetrahydrofluorene-2-one (IV)

(a). *Acid cyclisation*.—A mixture of the above crystalline compound (III, 550 mg., m.p. $78-79^{\circ}$), 6N-HCl (22 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (22 c.c.) was heated on a water-bath, under nitrogen, for 4 hours. The reaction mixture was diluted with a large excess of cold water and extracted several times with ether. The solvent was washed successively with water, saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and water. After removal of the dry solvent, the residue obtained was sublimed at $85-90^{\circ}/0.1$ mm to afford a white crystalline material (220 mg.), m.p. 93° with previous shrinking at 75° . This substance was very unstable at room temperature and did not furnish any semicarbazone. The above crystalline material (220 mg.) was chromatographed over alumina (6.6 g.) using petroleum ether as the eluting solvent. The white flaky crystals (140 mg.), thus obtained, was further purified by sublimation at $95-100^{\circ}/0.4$ mm to furnish the pure material, m.p. 95° , $\lambda_{\max}$ 257 μ ($\log \epsilon = 4.07$). (Found: C, 84.89; H, 7.09. $C_{15}H_{12}O$ requires C, 84.72; H, 6.52%).

(b). *Alkali cyclisation*.—To the compound (III, 0.4 g.) in boiled water (30 c.c.) was added a solution of KOH (85%, 0.4 g.) in boiled water (10 c.c.). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hours under nitrogen. Then, KOH (1.1 g.), dissolved in boiled water (10 c.c.), was added to make the alkali concentration 2.5%. The resulting mixture was refluxed for 6 hours more. On working up no product could be isolated.

1 : 2 : 3 : 4 : 10 : 11-Hexahydrofluorene-2-one (II)

The above crude solid compound (IV, 190 mg.), dissolved in ethanol (95%, 36 c.c.), was hydrogenated over palladium charcoal catalyst (10%, 110 mg.). The

theoretical amount of hydrogen was absorbed within one hour. The catalyst was filtered and the oily residue, obtained after evaporation of the solvent, was evaporatively distilled at 85-90°/0.2 mm to furnish a colorless viscous oil (450 mg.), $\lambda_{\max}$ 265 m μ (log ϵ 3.09).

The *semicarbazone* (100 mg.), m.p. 193° (crude), prepared from the above reduced product (100 mg.), was crystallised three times from methanol to furnish the pure material, m.p. 194-94.5°. (Found: C, 69.04; H, 7.02. C₁₄H₁₇ON₃, requires C, 69.13; H, 6.99%).

Dehydrogenation.—The above saturated ketone (300 mg.) was reduced by lithium aluminium hydride (150 mg.) by the usual procedure and the crude alcohol, thus obtained, was dehydrogenated by heating with selenium (500 mg.) at 295-305° for 14 hours. The reaction product was extracted with benzene and ether. The combined solvent was evaporated and the residue was sublimed at 80-95°/0.2 mm to yield a coloured crystalline material (140 mg.), m.p. 114-15°, which was recrystallised two times from methanol to furnish the pure compound, m.p. 116°. Mixed m.p. of this with an authentic sample of fluorene remained undepressed.

Methyl β -Carbomethoxy- β -(2-methylacetate-3-indenylidene)-propionate (V)

2-Bromohydrindone was prepared by following the procedure of Johnson *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1745). This compound was also prepared by Groves and Swan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 867). In our case, the temperature of bromination of 1-indanone was maintained at 0-5° throughout the operation. Only the dibromo compound could be isolated as the major product by adding bromine below 10° and then allowing the reaction mixture to stand at the room temperature (30°) for 2 hours. The concentration of the solvent (dry ether) in this reaction (cf. Johnson *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) appeared to be an important factor to avoid the formation of the dibromo compound.

Ethyl 1-keto-2-indanylmalonate was prepared from the above bromo compound according to the method of Groves and Swan (*loc. cit.*). The decarboxylation of the malonic ester system in the present case (cf. Groves and Swan, *loc. cit.*) was performed by refluxing the compound (18.1 g.) with a mixture of HCl (conc., 180 c.c.) and water (180 c.c.) for 24 hours. The mixture, on cooling in ice-bath, deposited 1-keto-2-indanylacetic acid (10 g.), m.p. 147°, which on crystallisation from hot water furnished the pure acid, m.p. 150-51° (reported m.p. 147-40°; Groves and Swan, *loc. cit.*).

The above crude acid (13 g.), on esterification with absolute methanol (100 c.c.) and H₂SO₄ (conc., 6 c.c.) by refluxing for 10 hours, afforded methyl 1-keto-2-indanylacetate (11.88 g.), b.p. 164-65°/1.5 mm.

Dimethyl succinate (11.63 g.) was added to a solution of potassium (2.2 g.) in dry *tert.*-butyl alcohol (42 c.c.) at room temperature (nitrogen atmosphere) and the mixture was stirred till homogeneous. To this solution was added the above keto-ester (7.88 g.) with *tert.*-butyl alcohol (8 c.c.) and the mixture was stirred

for 2 hours. As the yellow solution stood for 24 hours at room temperature (nitrogen atmosphere), it gradually turned to a deep red colour. The reaction mixture was then acidified with HCl (dil.) and most of the alcohol was distilled off at a reduced pressure. The pale yellow oily residue was taken up in ether and extracted with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. The combined extract was acidified and the precipitated oil was taken up in ether. The ethereal layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The yellow oily product, obtained on evaporation of the ether and removal of traces of the solvent, was esterified by refluxing with dry methanol (100 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 6 c.c.) for 12 hours. After usual working up, the residue, obtained after evaporation of the solvent, was distilled giving the desired unsaturated trimethyl ester as a straw-coloured oil (4.45 g.), b.p. 200-205°/0.4 mm, λ_{max} 272 m μ (log ϵ 4.14) and 300 m μ (log ϵ 4.00), leaving a higher boiling residue (3 g.). (Found: C, 65.17; H, 6.33. $C_{18}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 65.06; H, 6.02%). It may be mentioned that the esterification of the Stobbe product with diazomethane did not improve the yield of the compound (V).

The neutral ether extract from the above condensation was washed with water, dried, the ether removed, and the residue distilled, furnishing the unchanged keto-ester (0.65 g.), b.p. 150-55°/0.8 mm.

β -(2-Carboxymethyl-3-indenyl)-propionic Acid (VI: R=H).—The above unsaturated ester (4 g.) was refluxed for 3-4 hours with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (60 c.c.), HBr (48%, 40 c.c.) and water (20 c.c.). The acids were removed under reduced pressure and the residue, on cooling and diluting with cold water, deposited a coloured solid material which was filtered and dried to give the desired unsaturated acid (3.30 g.), m.p. 173-74°. A part of this material was crystallised two times from a mixture of ether-petroleum ether (60-80°) to furnish a fairly pure acid, m.p. 178-79°, which was recrystallised from dilute methanol (33%) to yield the pure acid, m.p. 179-80°, λ_{max} 259 m μ (log ϵ 4.00). (Found: C, 68.27; H, 5.80. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 68.29; H, 5.69%).

Methyl β -(2-Methylacetate-3-indenyl)-propionate (VI: R = Me).—The above unsaturated acid (1.65 g.), on esterification by an ethereal solution of diazomethane, prepared from nitrosomethylurea (4 g.), furnished the desired unsaturated ester (1.4 g.), evaporatively distilling at 120-25°/0.2 mm, λ_{max} 257 m μ (log ϵ 4.06). (Found: C, 70.45; H, 6.70. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 70.07; H, 6.56%).

Methyl β -(2-Methylacetate-3-indanyl)-propionate (VII).—The above unsaturated ester (1.1 g.) was catalytically reduced by 10% palladium on charcoal catalyst (200 mg.), as described before. The absorption of hydrogen, which was very fast at the start, was completed within one hour. The residue, obtained after removal of the catalyst and the solvent, was evaporatively distilled at 125-30°/0.4 mm to yield an oil (1.07 g.), λ_{max} 264 m μ (log ϵ 3.04). A portion was again evaporatively distilled for analysis. (Found: C, 69.32; H, 7.43. $C_{18}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 69.56; H, 7.24%).

1 : 2 : 3 : 4 : 10 : 11-Hexahydrofluorene-2-one (II)

(a). The above saturated ester (1.07 g.) was cyclised by refluxing for 6 hours with sodium hydride (0.17 g.) under dry benzene (25 c.c.) containing two drops of methanol. The reaction mixture was cooled, acidified with HCl (dil.) and extracted three times with ether. The combined extract was washed with cold water, dried and evaporated to give an oily residue which produced a deep violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. The residue was then hydrolysed by refluxing for 16 hours with 6N-HCl (50 c.c.). The cooled reaction mixture was worked up by the usual procedure and the neutral ketone, thus obtained, was evaporatively distilled at 85-95°/0.2 mm to afford an oil (0.27 g.). The *semi-carbazone* (100 mg.), m.p. 193°, obtained from the above ketone (100 mg.), was crystallised from methanol to furnish the pure material, m.p. 194°. The mixed m.p. of this semicarbazone with that obtained before, remained undepressed.

(b). The saturated ester (1.4 g.) was cyclised by refluxing for 6 hours with sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium dust (0.23 g.) and methanol (0.4 c.c.) in dry benzene (25 c.c.). After usual working up, the crude β -keto ester was hydrolysed by refluxing for 8 hours under nitrogen with a mixture of HCl (conc., 8 c.c.), glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) and water (4 c.c.). The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water and extracted two times with ether. The aqueous layer was neutralised by sodium bicarbonate and extracted three times with ether. The combined extract was washed with cold alkali solution (2%) and finally with water. After removal of the dry solvent, the neutral residue was evaporatively distilled at 90-100°/0.4 mm to furnish the desired ketone (0.46 g.). A pure sample, $\lambda_{\max}$ 256 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.09), was prepared for analysis by repeated evaporative distillation. (Found: C, 83.67; H, 7.58. C₁₃H₁₄O requires C, 83.87; H, 7.52%).

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